

THE BENEFITS OF THE HEALTH CARE ARE SOCIAL, ECONOMIC AND MEDICAL SYSTEMS

Student of SamSIFL:

RAHIMBERDIYEVA SHOHZODA SHERZODOVNA

Scientific supervisor : Senior teacher :

Sirojiddinova Shahribonu Sirojiddinovna

Email:sirojiddinovna1991@gmail.com

Abstract: Health systems have a benefit impact on the economic execution of their sectors in the national economy, through the jobs they device and from the purchase of goods and services. Thus, These days increasing of different disease that is why around the world search prevent these disease.

Key words: healthcare , private hospitals ,legal regulation ,drug , health policy

How health systems use and enclose their resources has phenomenon impact on the resulting economic, social and human benefits. By utilizing the resources and holdings within communities, and by taking responsible approaches to employment, job creation and the production of goods and attendance, health systems can transform local economies so that they work for everyone.

Health care includes general activities goal at preventing and treating diseases, producing healthy living and working conditions, ensuring high working capacity and longevity; its main task is to provide assistance to patients in a modern, specialized development and appropriate conduct. Health care has a long history in the East, especially in Uzbekistan. Especially in the Middle Ages, high layer of medicine were achieved in this region. Medical work were translated into Arabic, and their recommendations were put into practice. At the same time, thinkers of the East created extensive works on the science of medicine. The material and technical base of the Healthcare system in the country was gradually enlarged and

strengthened. It was necessary to open hospitals for wounded and damaged fighters, to further strengthen the material and technical base of the Health Care System, and to maintain a stable sanitary condition of the country. Soon, more than 130 military hospitals were opened, the Military Medical Academy in Leningrad, the Moscow Medical Institute and other medical research institutions were studied. Special surgical hospitals were opened in the republic for the treatment of war invalids. The reform of the public health protection sector began again, the main principle of the health care system is to restore the preventive direction; development and implementation of its modern and effective methods; strengthening maternal and child health protection sizes; improvement of the medical education system and personnel training; reorganization of scientific research based on the requirements of the era and society; to create an industry in the country that produces high-quality and sufficient quantities of pharmaceuticals, medical supplies, and technical tools related to this field; Further improvement of the material and technical base of healthcare institutions; The main task was to remove part of the treatment and prevention institutions from state ownership and change the form of possession. In Uzbekistan, great importance is attached to the continuity of medical education and the improvement of the qualifications of specialists. On the basis of this program, measures were taken to strengthen the primary link of health care and develop general medical practice. Wide networks of QVP were established in all regions, as a result, medical care was provided at two levels, that is, through QVP and the district central hospital. These works were carried out on the basis of the "Health" project in cooperation with the World Bank. This made it possible to develop new methods of management and financing of primary health care facilities, improve the quality of medical supplies and train general practical medical personnel. A new form of emergency medical care system has been introduced. As a result, it was possible to provide reserve medical care in all regions of the country, and to

significantly reduce the time between calling a doctor at home and providing qualified medical care. They train personnel and improve their qualifications, and provide medical assistance in emergency situations. The hospital has a reception area where the doctor examines the patient and prepares documents, rooms where the necessary sanitary-hygienic measures are taken, treatment departments , treatment-diagnostic departments such as radiology, physiotherapy, there will be laboratories, pharmacy, kitchen, administrative and economic departments, etc. The combined hospital also includes a polyclinic. The hospital is headed by a chief physician, and the specialized department where patients are treated is headed by a doctor qualified in that specialty. The head of the department of the united hospital can also be the head of the corresponding department in the polyclinic. The number of staff depends on the number of beds in the hospital. The structure and function of hospitals, as well as the rights, obligations. International legal standards on health care, basic rules for the organization of drug supply: WHO recommendations, advanced directions in pharmaceutical practice and pharmacist's ethics, international experience in the organization of drug supply. Specific features and main directions of development of the world pharmaceutical industry and the world pharmaceutical market, rules and main directions of pharmaceutical market regulation, processes of harmonization of regulatory requirements. Public method within the framework of the circulation of medicines. The legal basis for health care and medical care in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the conditions for the realization of constitutional rights, the drug supply system in the Republic of Uzbekistan: the state within the framework of the circulation of drugs in the Republic of Uzbekistan regulation by the main normative legal documents, the powers of state executive bodies for drug circulation, legal regulation of pre-clinical and clinical trials of drugs, legal regulation of drug registration, pharmaceutical control, regulation of drug production, drug standardization and quality control by the state.. Legal bases of

regulation of pharmaceutical activities The Law "On Medicines and Pharmaceutical Activities", essence, amendments. Understanding of pharmaceutical activity.

In general , health care is a system of social, economic and medical activities aimed at protecting the health of the population. Health care includes general activities aimed at preventing and treating diseases, creating healthy living and working conditions, ensuring high working capacity and longevity; its main task is to provide assistance to patients in a modern, specialized and appropriate manner

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